

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D5.2

**WP5 Advanced Technologies
Summary Position Paper**

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ABSTRACT

Work package 5 (WP5) of the HARPERS project aims to (a) identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning, (b) identify opportunities for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across Member States (MS), and (c) investigate and conclude on the need and benefits of the adoption of and more aligned approach to advanced technologies, to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Task 5.2 of the HARPERS project is focused on the refinement of the challenges and opportunities in adoption of advanced technologies, for three prioritised topic areas identified under Phase 1 of HARPERS (Task 5.1). The topics have been investigated further under Phase 2 (Task 5.2) through deeper engagement with the project's stakeholders using a range of methods such as surveys, questionnaires, and targeted workshops.

This document is a summary position paper setting out and evaluating the issues associated with the three prioritised topic areas, notably:

- New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration including waste treatment and immobilisation
- Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality. To include automation of waste sorting, application of smart decontamination techniques, segregation, sentencing, packaging and waste stores.
- 'Standardised' Digital Twin (DT) and advanced Building Information Management technology and their application, to include protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation, digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI) which will also benefit modelling protocols (3D).

Cross-topical findings have been identified based on (a) common barriers that are preventing the use of advanced technologies, and (b) recommendations to support

implementation of advanced technologies and to promote greater alignment of approaches at a European level.

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1. Introduction

The nuclear back-end comprises aspects related to the decommissioning of nuclear facilities, the management of spent nuclear fuel (SNF) and radioactive wastes as well as the remediation of sites, including legacy sites. These activities require specific tasks, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Typical tasks in the nuclear back-end.

The decommissioning of nuclear facilities is a time-consuming task that requires careful preparation and examination due to challenging radiological conditions and associated risks. These requirements also apply to the detailed planning of individual measures, e.g. the dismantling of large components, the decontamination of materials or the handling of radioactive residues/wastes. The spectrum of nuclear facilities is broad and covers facilities for fuel manufacturing, research reactors, nuclear power plants as well as fuel cycle and waste management facilities. Due to a lack of standardised facility designs and different facility histories, each facility is different from the decommissioning point of view. Therefore, a direct transfer of knowledge is often very difficult and only possible to a limited extent.

The complexity of decommissioning correlates strongly with the size of the plant (which in the case of reactors can be expressed in terms of reactor capacity, for example) and the intended use or the operational history. Power reactors are often at the forefront of public interest due to their number in conjunction with a comparatively high decommissioning complexity and due to their high relevance for the respective national waste management programme (handling and final disposal of irradiated fuel elements and other types of radioactive wastes across different waste categories). In addition,

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the decommissioning of reprocessing plants and/or legacy sites leads to unique challenges that can take several decades to solve.

As of 2023, around 200 power reactors have been shut down, of which around 20 have already been successfully decommissioned. In addition, around 450 research reactors and more than 150 other nuclear fuel cycle facilities have already been decommissioned. By the year 2050, it is expected that more than 200 power reactors, around 220 research reactors and more than 350 fuel cycle facilities will be permanently shut down [1].

An inventory of approximately 6.5 million cubic metres of radioactive waste is reported to exist world-wide [2], all of which will need to be stored, processed, and disposed of in accordance with the waste hierarchy (Figure 2).

Figure 2 The waste management hierarchy.

Around 86% of existing radioactive waste has very low level (VLLW) or low-level (LLW) radioactivity, while about ~14% is intermediate level waste (ILW) and less than 1% is high-level waste (HLW). As set out by IAEA guidance [3], all VLLW and LLW is suitable for disposal in (engineered) near-surface facilities, whereas (long-lived) ILW and HLW requires disposal at greater depths or – as the generally recognised option for HLW and SNF – in highly engineered deep geological disposal facilities (GDFs). As experience indicates, the technical, financial and political challenges of constructing a

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GDF are complex. At this point, most countries with a nuclear industry are in a site selection process. The Onkalo spent nuclear fuel repository in Finland will be the first operational GDF, with operation being expected for the year 2026. In general, the storage volume of such GDFs will be limited and, consequently, efforts need to be maximised to reduce the volume of waste being sentenced to GDFs and to use the available space as efficiently as possible.

Current practices take decommissioning into account during the design phase of a nuclear facility to prevent and minimise the generation of waste at source, e. g. by requiring a Preliminary Decommissioning Plan for nuclear new builds. However, historically, decommissioning and waste management received less consideration and has resulted in the generation of a complex and diverse nuclear waste inventory across Europe and worldwide.

Experience has shown that safe decommissioning of permanently shut-down reactors and other types of nuclear facilities is generally possible with the existing technical equipment. However, there are good reasons to improve or standardise existing technical methods and to develop innovative technologies, for example to exploit optimisation potential (e.g. to reduce the radiation dose for employees, to increase process safety, to minimise secondary wastes or to reduce costs) while ensuring and improving safety and security aspects. In addition to this improvement of the status quo, new decommissioning techniques are also critical for the decommissioning of damaged reactors and some legacy sites.

Due to the foreseeable permanent plant shutdowns, the importance of nuclear back-end activities will increase internationally in the near future. Innovative technical methods, that are currently under development, offer improvements compared to established methods and therefore have a good chance of being utilised in practice in the coming decades. The effective treatment of operational wastes, reclaimed contaminated sites and residues from decommissioning is essential to enable effective and efficient waste management, to identify opportunities for reuse and recycle, and to design waste packages that can be safely handled, stored, transported and disposed of. Effective treatment, in turn, requires the development and use of innovative waste management and decommissioning technologies.

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Decommissioning Research and Development (R&D) is often cross-cutting and not limited to specific tasks. There are also cross-sector approaches, such as robotics or digital tools (e.g. Building Information Modelling (BIM)), which provide opportunities to optimise work and processes compared to the established practice. A mandatory prerequisite for the use of innovative technologies is a detailed proof of suitability and quality, the details of which are based in practice on the (radiological) risk potential of the application. This proof includes, for example, non-radioactive tests, radioactive laboratory-scale assessments, engineering-scale replica tests, on-plant radioactive trials and evidence of existing recovery options for technical equipment in the event of failures or risk assessments. This evidence must then be positively assessed by multiple stakeholders (e.g. the competent authority, technical experts etc.). The effort involved cannot be underestimated and, especially for those who have had no previous contact with the nuclear industry, difficult to comprehend in full detail, e.g. in terms of the required depth of testing. In addition to that, there are various further challenges that may prevent the practical use of innovative technologies. It is therefore strongly advised to analyse existing obstacles that innovative technologies are currently facing and to indicate possibilities to reduce the associated barriers without compromising safety and security.

1.1. HARPERS WP5 context

Work Package 5 (WP5) of the EU-project HARPERS has the following aims, to:

- a) Identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning
- b) Identify opportunities for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across Member States (MS)
- c) Investigate and conclude on the need and benefits of the adoption of a more aligned approach to advanced technologies, to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

During the first phase of the project, the objective of WP5 was to identify and prioritise the needs and opportunities for advanced technologies. Based on the input of the project partners, interested external stakeholders, and a literature review, various

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topics of interest were identified that could be grouped into three categories: Waste treatment, automation/robotics and digitalisation. Afterwards, these topics were discussed with external stakeholders and prioritised, leading to three subtasks being selected for the second phase of the HARPERS project [4]:

- Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilisation (5a)
- Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management (5b)
- Standardising Digital Twin (DT) and Advanced Building Information Management¹ Technology and their Application (5c)

The main purpose of these three subtasks was to provide a transparent picture of the barriers that innovative technologies are currently facing and to provide recommendations to mitigate these challenges without compromising safety and security, e.g. by unlocking the potential of standardisation and adopting more aligned approaches across MS.

This position paper provides a summary of the main cross-topical findings of these tasks. For this purpose, the underlying methodology is summarised in section 2. Critical aspects of each task are summarised in section 3. The cross-topical findings are provided in section 4, with a short summary following in section 5.

An additional detailed paper, covering more information about the individual analysis and findings of the three subtasks is in preparation [5]. Further to this, information on regulatory and business case aspects have been incorporated into independent reports published by the HARPERS consortium [6, 7].

¹ In Phase 1 of HARPERS, reference was made to the broader term Building Information Management, while under Phase 2, the more specific term/technology Building Information Modelling has been used.

2. Methodology

2.1. TECOP framework

Various established frameworks exist for project management and risk assessment purposes that facilitate a structured approach to collating and assessing information, relevant factors and their role regarding benefits, barriers or risks. One well-established example is the TECOP (Technical, Environmental, Commercial, Operational, and (socio-)Political) framework to identify risks under a suite of project management rules, guidance and documentation, but it can also be used within a wider frame, e.g. to evaluate benefits and barriers.

The TECOP framework was adopted early in the HARPERS project to categorise some of the key enablers and blockers to technology development, to support the creation of questionnaires and data gathering, and to facilitate the inclusion of information sources and perspectives from stakeholders. The TECOP framework was also utilised in all the WP5 subtasks as detailed in Figure 3.

Figure 3 An illustration of the TECOP framework and its application in WP5.

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2.2. Stakeholder Map, Engagement and Data Acquisition

The implementation of advanced technologies requires involvement of different parties/stakeholders, as illustrated in Figure 4:

- **Policy Makers (PM)** set and establish rules and procedures.
- **Regulators (R)** define the boundary conditions with the regulatory framework.
- **Supervisory Authorities (SA)** that are responsible for ensuring that regulatory requirements are fulfilled.
- **Operators (O)** are usually also the license holders and are the project managers.
- **Service Providers (SP)** can support the operators (contract award) by performing specific tasks or by providing technical solutions.
- **Supply Chain (SC)** provide components, including spare parts, and/or complete systems.
- **Technology Developers (R&D)** are responsible for the development of technologies or parts thereof. Examples are given in terms of universities, R&D facilities or commercial R&D companies.
- **Technical and Scientific Support Organisations (TSO²)** provide expertise to the nuclear regulatory body of their respective country.
- **Standards committees (SC)** develop technical norms to harmonise practical approaches.
- **International organisations (IO)**, including the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA) and Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), foster the exchange between various stakeholders and have the ambition to ensure and to improve safety.
- **Funding Bodies (FB)** can provide financial support to specific projects on a national or international level. Usually, the kind of supported activities are specified in a dedicated funding programme.
- The **workforce (W)** consists of those people using technical tools to achieve progress.

² This abbreviation is also used for "Technical Safety Organisation".

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- Members of the **public (P)** are not involved in the immediate activities, but public opinion is taken into account for nuclear back-end activities, e. g. in terms of public participation as an integral part of decommissioning planning or site selections.
- **Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO)** are independent organisations that focus on specific humanitarian or social issues.

Figure 4 Stakeholder Map. The double arrows represent strong bilateral connections between stakeholders regarding the implementation of advanced technologies. The dashed lines indicate for which stakeholders funding opportunities provide opportunities to advance the R&D related to advanced technologies.

To incorporate the perspectives and opinions from nuclear professionals and organisations within and outside the HARPERS consortium, each subtask issued a questionnaire in spring/summer 2024³. These questionnaires were shared with

³ Available to view at: <https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/news-events/news/harpers-wp5-advanced-technologies-questionnaire.html>

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stakeholders over a three-month period by different means (e.g., announcements on the HARPERS website, social media, personal networks, or international conferences / working parties) and feedback was collated and reviewed. The questionnaires shared a similar structure with questions divided into six categories that covered general aspects as well as aspects related to the TECOP categories. The number of replies to this first questionnaire are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 Responses to the first questionnaires issued mid-2024

	Subtask 5.2A “Decontamination”	Subtask 5.2B “Robotics”	Subtask 5.2C “DT and BIM”
Service-Provider / end-user	3	1	3
R&D	8	1	7
Operator	9	1	2
Regulator	2	1	-
Supervisory Authority	-	-	2
Consultancy	1	-	1
Other	1	1	-
Total	24	5	15

Due to the different number of questionnaire responses, the three subtask groups followed different approaches for their analysis. While the group working on subtask 5.2A focused their analysis on the feedback provided to this initial questionnaire, the groups working on subtasks 5.2B and 5.2C identified barriers and developed recommendations whose relevance could then be assessed by external stakeholders. For this assessment, both groups issued a second questionnaire and gathered information by the end of 2024. Unfortunately, replies to the second questionnaire were also sparse, which consequently led to larger uncertainties.

On 14th October 2024, WP5 organised an online workshop, to which external stakeholders were also invited. The main purpose of this meeting, which involved 24 participants, was to present and to discuss the preliminary findings identified by the different subtask groups.

3. Information on Subtasks

3.1. Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilisation

Legacy nuclear facilities frequently contain a wide range of different physical, chemical and radiological hazards which are poorly characterised, difficult to access and in turn hard to decontaminate. This can often result in people having to work hands-on in dangerous environments and operations being conducted that generate significant volumes of secondary waste. Various advanced decommissioning and waste management technologies are being developed to overcome the industry's complex challenges (examples given in [5]). However, a range of common barriers are experienced which hinder their development and wider application, including:

- A lack of detailed plant records and operational histories to baseline the scale of the challenge
- The lack of availability of clear and common disposal routes and the associated Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)
- Limited availability of characterisation data quality objectives (DQO) and characterisation capability
- Lack of shared understanding on existing technologies and their Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
- Limited access to radioactive materials and testing facilities to demonstrate advanced technologies
- Uncertainty related to licensing, market size, operator appetite and current waste disposal/treatment method costs
- Lack of common shared assumptions for Cost Benefit Analysis

Subtask 5.2A focused specifically on understanding how standardising approaches to technology assessment and qualification for decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation could benefit existing and future decommissioning practices, both in Europe and globally. A more detailed list of

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identified common barriers and potential solutions identified via the TECOP exercise in this subtask can be found in Appendix 1. A discussion of how this data was inferred from the stakeholder engagements exercise is provided in [5].

If successfully achieved, the benefits of implementing advanced technologies on a wide scale include:

- Reduced hands-on work and radiation dose to workers
- Re-classification and volume reduction of the waste requiring near- and sub-surface disposal
- Improved options for decommissioning strategy development and safety case planning
- Deployment of faster and more efficient processes
- Processing of problematic / orphan waste streams
- Cost reductions (as a result of the above)

3.2. Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management

The nuclear back-end covers activities such as the planned decommissioning of nuclear facilities, the management of SNF and radioactive wastes, as well as the remediation of sites. Each of these activities requires measures for which technical solutions are mandatory, see Figure 1. For this purpose, robots have the potential to provide added value, including:

- Reduction of operator exposures to hazardous conditions
- More efficient use of personnel
- Remote operation capabilities to allow intervention in inaccessible or dangerous areas without direct human presence
- Optimisation of the risk assessment, including safety risks and project risks
- Efficient decision making as a result of automated data collection and data analysis
- Improved asset utilisation through enhanced capabilities of robots, leading to better capital efficiency

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- Reduction of operational costs due to reduced labour costs, minimised impact of human errors and automated repetitive actions/activities
- Reduction of time-consuming and recurring preparations, e.g. related to putting on personal protective equipment
- Increasing attractiveness to new generation workforces

In addition, robots are usually required for the decommissioning of legacy sites (e.g. Sellafield, La Hague) and complex decommissioning projects (e.g. Fukushima and Chernobyl) due to unique challenges arising from potential risks and radiation levels.

Due to the benefits that robots can provide, different kinds of robots have been developed or adopted that fulfil the unique requirements of the nuclear sector. However, despite the fundamental advantages that robots and automated systems can provide, impediments exist that currently still limit the number of applications, especially those with a high level of automation. A thorough understanding of such barriers from different points of view is essential to find solutions that reduce these impediments without compromising safety and security. Here, it should be noted that the on-going activities of the *Expert Group on the Application of Robotics and Remote Systems in the Nuclear Back-end* (EGRRS) include aspects such as the implementation of robotics and the analysis of certain barriers and the provision of recommendations (e. g. in terms of cost-benefit analysis) [8, 9].

The strong need for reducing such barriers has also been supported by the stakeholder engagement during the first phase of the HARPERS project, during which certain needs have been identified, including:

- Guidance (including from regulators) and sharing experience on demonstrating safety and security to regulators (safety case), appropriate to the environment of application (basic to harsh)
- Communication routes with regulators during technology development
- Standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces, including standardised architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages

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- Transfer of knowledge/technologies from other industries and sharing experience on evaluation and use of robotics on sites, for different applications
- Evaluate new procedures/protocols to integrate automation and robots or drones in the nuclear environment (e.g. Indoor use of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV))
- Internationally aligned practices

The main purpose of this subtask was to address barriers that impede the use of robotics in the nuclear back-end and to provide selected recommendations – with a special attention to standardisation – that may lead to a reduction of such barriers. The investigated barriers and recommendations are listed in Appendix 2.

3.3. Standardising Digital Twin and Advanced Building Information Management

The nuclear industry, particularly in its back-end operations, is increasingly recognising the need for digitalisation to enhance efficiency, safety, and cost-effectiveness. As nuclear facilities age and decommissioning becomes a pressing concern, digital technologies offer innovative solutions to complex challenges. DTs and BIM are emerging as powerful tools in nuclear back-end operations. The potential impact of these technologies includes:

- Improved safety through reduced human exposure to radiation by enabling remote planning and visualisation of decommissioning activities
- Enhanced waste estimation and management, allowing for more accurate predictions of waste volumes and types
- Optimised decommissioning planning and execution, leading to cost savings and shorter project timelines
- Better risk assessment and scenario planning for various dismantling approaches
- Increased transparency and collaboration among stakeholders through shared digital platforms
- Enhanced regulatory compliance and documentation through comprehensive digital records
- Improved integration of robotics and automation in decommissioning processes

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- More accurate cost estimation and budget management for decommissioning projects

It is noted that both DTs and BIM are gaining traction in the nuclear back-end, with some real-world implementations demonstrating their value. For instance, at the Fessenheim nuclear reactor in France⁴, automated BIM modelling technologies coupled with building point clouds were used to create a static DT, which proved crucial in preparing for future dismantling operations. Another example was demonstrated in the UK via the use of the REBIM[®] common data environment (CDE) at Sellafield⁵, where it has been employed to demonstrate the potential for future-proofing the Operations and Maintenance (O&M) phase of a new flask maintenance facility supporting nuclear decommissioning. These examples showcase the practical application of DTs and BIM in nuclear decommissioning and waste management. Despite these advancements and the fact that some countries now mandate BIM for projects exceeding certain values, the adoption of these technologies in the nuclear back-end still lags behind other industries, indicating significant room for growth and further implementation.

By analysing the gaps in implementing DT and BIM in the nuclear back-end, based on the literature survey and the opinions of various stakeholders, some of the critical needs and recommendations were highlighted. These include:

- Creating customised DT and BIM solutions through cross-sector technological collaboration
- Establishing international standards and guidelines for DT and BIM in nuclear back-end operations
- Implementing an incremental adoption strategy focusing on high-priority decommissioning tasks
- Conducting cost-benefit analyses and pilot projects to demonstrate the long-term economic benefits, operational efficiencies, and environmental improvements

⁴ <https://www.assystem.com/en/publications/digital-twin-a-winning-equation-for-the-nuclear-industry/>

⁵ <https://rebim.io/bim-in-operations-and-maintenance-phase-for-nuclear-decommissioning-at-sellafield/>

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- Building specialised workforce training programs bridging nuclear engineering and digital skills
- Promoting public understanding and international collaboration for technology adoption

Subtask 5.2C focuses on defining the barriers that impede the adoption of DT and BIM in the nuclear back-end and providing a set of recommendations to the relevant stakeholders. The investigated barriers and recommendations are listed in Appendix 3.

4. Cross-Topical Findings

A key observation held by the various stakeholders during this work was that many of the identified barriers and proposed recommendations were not limited to just one subtask. Such cross-topical findings are the focus of this section. Further discussion of the specific subtask-related information is captured in [5].

An overview of the identified barriers and recommendations which were common to at least two of the subtasks is provided in Table 2. Many of the identified cross-cutting barriers preventing the use of advanced technologies were relevant to multiple TECOP categories. The suggested solutions that have been identified for harmonisation at a European level can be grouped and categorised as follows:

1. Establish European Working Group(s) for Common Challenges

Establishment of European platforms to promote and facilitate discussions between different stakeholders and to foster cross-industry exchange and collaboration. The working groups created would focus on high impact challenges for which the proposed advanced technologies offer clear safety and / or economic benefits against shared objectives and goals.

2. Develop Common Guidelines and Identification of Good Practices

Development of universal standards, protocols and guidelines to support standardised assessment and implementation of advanced technologies across borders (e.g. cyber assessments). There is a cross-topical need for guidance and technical norms that will provide an added value for both end-users and regulators / supervisory authorities.

3. Creation and Maintenance of a Centralised Knowledge Database

Implementation of a centralised and easy-to-access database of existing technologies and case studies to share learning and experience. Varied stakeholder communication will be vastly improved with a shared point of referenceable information.

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4. Cross-Border Harmonisation of Test Facilities

Creation of European sand-box⁶ approaches and facilities to support testing with respect to development and regulation of new technologies. Skills, costs and risks could then be shared and common ways of working agreed and then adopted.

5. Standardised Training and Certification Programmes

Implementation of universally recognised training courses and certification supported by digital tools. This would enable developers to ensure the impact of new technologies on safety and efficiency is well demonstrated and a limited work force could be shared between facilities.

6. Establish a Shared Methodology for Business Case Analysis

Development of a standardised methodology for conducting cost-benefit analysis with shared industry assumptions. There is a requirement to adequately compare the long-term cost consequences of acting and non-acting in decommissioning strategy planning, in addition to the costs and risks associated with doing work manually, against the cost of developing, manufacturing, testing and deploying technological alternatives. This would also help long term work force planning, knowledge management and common life cycle assessments.

⁶ While there is no agreed definition, sand-boxes generally refer to tools allowing businesses to test and experiment with new and innovative products, services or businesses under supervision of a regulator for a limited period of time.

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Table 2 Cross-Topical Findings in WP5

Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
General Aspects						
Stakeholder communication	Restrictive working relationships between key stakeholders leading to an inability to concisely identify shared objectives and goals.	✓	✓	✓	Establish facilitated platforms to stimulate discussion between various stakeholders (e.g. to raise awareness of impediments and opportunities) and make the results and findings easy-to-access.	SC, R&D, R, O, SA SA
Shared awareness of technical solutions	Lack of shared knowledge and awareness of details on existing technologies and their Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	✓	✓	✓	Creation of a centralised, easy-to-access and maintained database on existing technologies (e.g. TRL status, deployment, operational and waste specifications, advantages, limitations, case studies etc.) to create a shared stakeholder awareness	O, SP, FB, TD, FB, W
Risk Aversion	The nuclear sector often lags behind other industries in developing and deploying innovative technologies, possibly due to a risk averse culture	✓	✓	✓	Foster cross-industry exchange that also addresses the standards for the implementation of new technologies in the nuclear back-end.	R&D, TSO, R, SA, O, SP, SC, IO

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Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
Regulatory requirements	Country-specific regulatory frameworks can hinder adoption of new technologies across borders and often lead to increased costs, e.g. due to requalifications.	✓	✓	✓	Development of universal technical standards to streamline requirements across borders.	R, O, SP, R&D
Cyber security	Lacking awareness and understanding of (cyber) security aspects, e.g. by developers, the supply chain and end users.	✓	✓	✓	Develop and enforce strong cybersecurity protocols to protect sensitive information. Provision of dedicated training measures.	TD, SP, O, W
Technical Aspects						
Standardised development and assessment protocols	Unclear requirements to demonstrate confidence and suitability of system technology in end environment, resulting in re-work and poor technical integration	✓	✓	✓	Standardisation of assessment procedures and awareness of technology development, integration and deployment processes (including lifetime requirements such as maintenance)	SC, R&D, R, O, SA

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Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
International test facilities	Limited access to radioactive materials and testing facilities to demonstrate and validate advanced technologies.	✓	✓		Creation of European sand-box facilities to aid ease of scale-up, versatile deployment and implementation under usual business when developing technologies.	TD, SP, O, FB, SA, R
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>						
Varied approach to First-of-a-Kind (FOAK) technology demonstrations	Lack of a consolidated approach for regulating FOAK technologies. Existing regulations not enabling measures to be put in place that are proportional to risk.	✓	✓		Develop and collaborate through 'regulatory sand-boxes' to uncover deeper learning and manage emerging technologies.	R&D, R, SP, FB, SA, O, SC
Identification of relevant specific guidance and regulatory requirements	Challenge in identifying which guidance and regulatory requirements are most relevant for stakeholders involved in the development of advanced technologies	✓	✓	✓	Development of international standards and guidelines that address the mandatory requirements for implementation of advanced technologies.	R, SA, SP, R&D, O

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Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
Varied certification process	Challenges arising from country-specific legislation and certification mechanisms	✓	✓	✓	Review and when necessary update and standardise regulatory frameworks to accommodate the development and integration of advanced technologies.	IO, R, TSO
Commercial Aspects						
Cost-Benefit-Analysis	Uncertainty about the economic justification for initial investments. Lack of realistic and shared accepted cost projections / models / assumptions, due to uncertainties associated with forecasting lifecycle costs (particularly for many decades into the future), to support effective Cost Benefit Analysis.	✓	✓	✓	Focus on tasks for which the proposed systems offer clear safety and / or economic benefits. Establishing means of adequately comparing the long-term cost consequences of acting and non-acting, and also means of comparing the costs and risks associated with doing work manually against the cost of developing, manufacturing, testing and deploying technological alternatives.	TD, FB, SP, O
Incentivisation and graded approach	High initial costs (including training) to implementation	✓	✓	✓	Provide modular solutions that allow nuclear facilities to implement specific features incrementally, reducing initial investment costs and complexity. Offer financial incentives or tax breaks to nuclear facilities that adopt advanced technologies.	TD, FB, SP, O

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Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
IP Management	Holders of intellectual property rights can restrict access to information about their products which can lead to higher costs (e.g. for maintenance or disposal).	✓	✓		Improved business culture with respect to embracing new technologies, and the need to establish a clear use case to support challenge statements.	TD, SP, O, Int, FB, R
Quality assurance	Lack of solid evidence demonstrating return on investment, and incomplete picture of the benefits.	✓	✓	✓	Clear guidance to enable developers to ensure the impact of new technologies on safety and efficiency is well demonstrated.	FB, R, SP
Operational Aspects						
Facility transition from Operations to Decommissioning	Challenges along the transition from productive operation to cost-generating decommissioning and dismantling (D&D)	✓		✓	Effective management and transparent communication to support the transfer of viewpoint and personnel from operations to D&D. Involve operational personnel at all stages of design and development to ensure practical insights that enhance safety and usability.	O, W, SA, R
Organisational factors	Organisational aspects impeding innovations, including staff requirements, necessary initial investments and integration into existing systems and processes.	✓	✓	✓	Provision of suitable and standardised training measures supported by digital tools, if needed. Allocation of sufficient budgets to build competencies, including upskilling.	O, W, SP

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Category	Challenge	Subtask Alignment			Recommendation	Key Stakeholders (Section 2.2)
		5.2A	5.2B	5.2C		
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>						
Public opinion	Lack of public acceptance, e. g. due to concerns regarding safety and environmental impacts.		✓	✓	Emphasise the benefits for society and outline potential future applications to gain the support, prioritise transparency, community engagement and open dialogue.	P, PM,R
Funding	Lack of adequate / consistent funding and financial support for the development of new technologies.	✓	✓		Provision of funding to advance promising low-TRL (TRL 1 to TRL 6) technologies, thereby enabling the development and testing needed for future deployment.	FB, TD, SP
Loss of workforce	Loss of institutional knowledge and challenging recruitment. Workforce and resource challenges can lead to the loss of experienced personnel and poor knowledge transfer.	✓	✓		Provide adequate budgets to implement a structured knowledge management system to ensure that institutional knowledge is spread among different people and captured with suitable means. Use of mentors to assist new professionals.	O, SP, TD

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5. Summary and Outlook

Advanced technologies have the potential to improve the safety and security of all nuclear related activities. Therefore, it is in the interest of the nuclear sector and the public that any required new technologies become implemented in a timely fashion – always under the strict requirement that there are no compromises regarding safety and security. It should be noted that the use of such technologies is not necessarily restricted to current nuclear back-end activities. It is likely that these technologies - in combination with the gained experience and knowledge during the R&D process – can also provide added value to other areas of investment in future nuclear developments including new-builds – such as Advanced Nuclear Technologies (e.g. High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGRs)), Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), Gen 3+4 and fusion reactors – and also other highly regulated industries.

As pointed out in the cross-topical findings, many of the barriers related to the implementation of advanced technologies are related to a lack-of-information and difficult-to-find or missing information (including guidance and norms) for the key stakeholders, including decision makers and business case developers. Keeping in mind that – unlike the nuclear front end – the majority of nuclear back-end activities (such as decommissioning) usually does not lead to additional revenues (for the facility owner), the perception of cost benefits and investment, is different. Hence, having a strong business case that clearly sets out the benefits of risk reduction and/or cost savings for implementation of advanced technologies in the nuclear back-end is therefore essential.

It is obvious that advanced technologies will have certain implications for the workforce, e. g. human factors considerations, qualification requirements and the required number of workers needed for specific tasks. Therefore, an essential requirement for a successful and safe application of new technologies is the acceptance by those who will have to work with them.

Within this report, several recommendations for the reduction of implementation barriers were expressed. In general, it can be stated, that the perception of barriers

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and the relevance of recommendations usually depends on the different stakeholder perspectives. Hence, communication and alignment of purpose and understanding between different stakeholders is a key element to gain a better understanding of different needs and problems. Activities that should promote greater alignment of approaches at a European level to support implementation of advanced technologies have been identified in the previous Cross-Topical Findings section.

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Appendix 1 – Summary of findings from subtask 5.2A

Table 3 Summary of Identified Barriers for Subtask 5.2A

<i>Technical Aspects</i>
Restrictive working relationships between key stakeholders (e.g. tech developer, waste owner/receiver, regulators etc.) leading to inability to concisely identify shared key objective / goals
Existing regulator guidance being too broad, lagging behind technological advancements and open for interpretation, leading to hesitation and variability in implementation.
Lack of detailed plant records and operational histories to underline the extent of contamination and the scale of the challenge
Limited availability of characterisation data quality objectives (DQO) and characterisation capability
Lack of shared understanding on existing technologies and their Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
Limited access to radioactive materials and testing facilities to demonstrate advanced technologies
The availability of clear disposal routes (including reuse and recycling) and the associated Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>
Limited awareness of existing guideline documents that support the design, development and deployment of new and innovative waste management and decommissioning technologies (e.g. safety, operational efficiency)
Challenge in identifying which guidance is most relevant for the development of innovative technologies, and which organisations need to be engaged with from the outset, leading to prolonged development timelines
Existing guidance too open for interpretation by experts at different stages of technology development cycle
Too much variability in existing documents (e.g. site dependent)
Existing regulations not enabling measures to be put in place that are proportional to risk

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Lack of dialogue between technology developers and facility operators
<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Uncertainty related to licensing, market size, operator appetite and current waste disposal/treatment method costs
Insufficient data quality to allow appropriate characterisation of legacy and new wastes
Resistance to undertaking appropriate sampling and analysis to provide requisite data was frequent, coupled with lack of available characterisation services
Technology developers reluctant to share IP for waste assessments
Lack of realistic and accepted cost projections/models, due to uncertainties associated with forecasting lifecycle costs (particularly for many decades into the future), to support effective Cost Benefit Analysis
Countries are not always given equal consideration given the discrepancies in waste disposal costs
Current practices tend towards parallel development and projects across various sites during decommissioning phase, resulting in overlapping scopes and work duplication
Limited operator appetite for innovation due to the risks and long delays associated with developing a new technology and making it robust. Leads to preference to implement on-the-shelf solutions rather than commit to developing a new approach.
Missing discussion on acceptable risk. Zero risk is very expensive and delays projects.
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Loss of knowledge and experience during transition between operational to decommissioning safety cases
Managing viewpoint shift from operations to decommissioning
Variable duty holder expectations regarding the implementation of different procedures for the operation and maintenance of advanced technologies
Low risk appetite held by key stakeholders for advanced technology demonstration and deployment

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<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>
Risk aversion and conservative mindsets limit the adoption of advanced technologies, despite clear potential long-term benefits.
Inefficient communication between the various stakeholders (R&D, operators, regulators etc), including governmental bodies and the wider public.
Political influence and constrained funding cycles inhibit incentivisation for facility duty holders to offer their facilities and resources for advanced technology demonstration. This does not aid educational and skill gaps.
Workforce and resource challenges leads to the loss of experienced personnel and poor knowledge transfer. High employee turnover and a lack of independence to address these issues impact stability and progress.
Fragmented regulatory frameworks lead to a lack of understanding regarding new technologies and existing capability. Country's unique regulatory requirements slow down the adoption of new technologies and increase costs due to the need for requalification and compliance with different standards.

Table 4 Summary of Recommended Solutions for Subtask 5.2A

<i>Technical Aspects</i>
Creation of European sand-box facilities to aid standardised TRL progression, aid versatile deployment designs and implementation under usual business projects when developing technologies. This would also improve accessibility to radioactive test facilities, in addition to facilitating consistent engagement between technical expertise.
Take benefits of international practice and adopt characterisation data quality objectives related to characterisation (not only radiological)

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Develop existing cross-border guidance, with a focus on ensuring it is interpreted uniformly. This could include harmonisation of definitions. Currently, the same terminology is used in multiple countries, but interpreted differently (for example, very low level waste (VLLW)).
Develop standardised waste conditioning and disposal routes for common intermediate level waste (ILW) and high level waste (HLW) challenges across countries (e.g. ion exchange resins). Underground disposal facilities will be limited in capacity
Establish standardised guidance on evaluating common uncertainties (e.g., risk, costs etc.)
Focus investment on technologies that are reusable, recyclable, sustainable and have accurate life cycle analysis
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>
Develop existing regulator and operational guideline documents with the support of dedicated experts to include details on the testing and assessment of advance technology developments.
Adopt a standardised process to establishing and maintaining communication with plant owners and waste recipients to promote compliance
Develop and collaborate through 'regulatory sand-boxes' to uncover deeper learning and manage emerging technologies. These types of strategies can be supplemented with option studies
Promote flexibility with regards to existing waste packages and the development of new containers / disposal routes. Support with malleable authorisation to optimise a given decommissioning or radioactive waste management process
<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Establish a standardised costing methodology of current techniques and common assumptions. This is required for the assessment of market opportunities for advanced technologies and full life-cycle assessment.
Internationally recognised incentives to encourage interest and demonstration of advanced technologies. This would help change conservative mindsets and help view demonstrations as core business work.
Establishing standardised means of adequately comparing the long-term cost consequences of acting and non-acting, and also means of comparing the costs and risks associated with doing work manually against the cost of developing, manufacturing, testing and deploying technological alternatives

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Introduce guidance setting out standardised certifications for advanced technologies prior to on-plant demonstrations.
Improve efficiency by aligning projects which have similar technology development goals and commercial processes
Implement a risk-based, graded approach to technology development to avoid overworked technical solutions
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Establish international standards for knowledge management
Production of accessible technology briefing packs owned by an international authority to improve local understanding of novel technologies and to promote amenability of local staff (mitigate rigid mindsets)
Development of guideline documents through active engagement between regulators, site licensees and other stakeholders to help reduce the variability in duty holder expectations
Facilitate communication on technology development (e.g. via hubs, communities of practice, centres of excellence, cross-functional teams or technical working groups etc.) to ensure perceived risks and approaches to hazard management are properly articulated. Emphasise the development of technologies that are readily demonstrable and compatible with end-users
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>
Develop standardised data and knowledge transfer strategies to help prevent knowledge and skills gaps.
Increased stakeholder and public engagement. Transparent communication and proactive public involvement can help build trust. In-depth engagement ensures transparent descriptions of whole life-cycle impacts of an emerging technology. Operational staff should be engaged throughout development
Regulatory Harmonisation. Standardising regulatory frameworks across countries could reduce requalification costs and facilitate smoother technology adoption.
Support for International Cooperation - smaller countries with limited resources could benefit from international cooperation. Sharing best practices, standardised training programs, and knowledge transfer could help address disparities
Focused Investment and Risk Management. Strategic funding allocation and clearer guidance from senior management and government bodies can support innovation

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Standardised risk assessment frameworks and cost-benefit analyses could provide a compelling case for new technologies, overcoming reluctance due to conservative mindsets.

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Appendix 2 - Summary of findings from subtask 5.2B

Table 5 Summary of Identified Barriers for Subtask 5.2B

<i>General Aspects</i>
Reluctance to work with “first-of-a-kind” (FOAK) technology.
Lack of detailed reference materials that focus on the necessary steps towards the implementation of robotic technologies in the nuclear back-end.
Lack of knowledge on existing robotic solutions to address challenges in the nuclear back-end.
Challenges with the adoption of robotic solutions and automated solutions from other industries.
<i>Technical Aspects</i>
Difficulty integrating new robotic systems with existing, fixed physical and software interfaces.
Lacking awareness and global availability of proven systems.
Avoidance of defaulting to single-purpose use when not required (focus on single-purpose use).
Lack of transparency due to restricted information due to Intellectual Property (IP) / security restrictions, resulting in inefficient design, maintenance strategies, increased waste.
Lack of standardised list of technology reliability in radiation fields, resulting in sub—optimal maintenance strategies.
Difficulty in creation of lifetime maintenance plans, including lack of information sharing regarding radiation tolerance and safety-optimal maintenance strategies.
Challenges in implementing the technical automation of complex or highly variable tasks, including proving suitability of system to necessary confidence levels.
Communication disruptions and difficulties with wireless communications.
TRL 1-7 (idea generation and development) is the area with the greatest technical challenges.

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Unclear requirements to prove (e.g. to the regulator) confidence and suitability of system in end environment, resulting in re-work and poor technical integration.
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>
Insufficient consideration of the possibility for decontamination and disposability in the design process, which can lead to higher costs and radioactive waste.
Lack of awareness of sustainability in decommissioning operations and equipment lifecycle management.
Lack of awareness of security aspects by developers and vendors of robotic components (e.g. the use of Clouds).
Lack of technical standards for developers and end-users/operators.
Difficulty in verifying and validating that automated and robotic systems using Artificial Intelligence (AI) are suitable for tasks in a variety of operating environments, from low radiation to highly hazardous zones.
Challenges arising from country-specific legislation and certification mechanisms.
Developers/end users are unaware of existing regulatory requirements (e.g. for safety and security aspects) that the technology has to fulfil, which can cause delays and project uncertainties.
Lack of a consolidated approach for regulating First-of-a-Kind technologies.
<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Incomplete picture of the benefits related to automation and/or robotics, leading to an uncertain cost-benefit model.
Automated and/or robotic systems are too task specific, so the possibilities for recouping investments are limited.
The “equipment life-cycle costs are too high.” [9]
High initial costs (including training) to implement automated and/or robotic systems.
“Lack of qualified vendors.” [9]
Holders of intellectual property rights can restrict access to information about their products which can lead to higher costs (e.g. for maintenance or disposal).
High costs and long timeframes associated with obtaining certifications for AI and robotic systems in nuclear applications.

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High additional costs to develop radiation-hardened robots.
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Automated and/or robotic systems are too complex to use which can lead to additional risks.
Concerns regarding the performance in a nuclear environment.
Lack of knowledge across an organisation.
Limited training, that is not focused on the customer's specific application.
Reluctance of workforce to use automated/robotic systems.
Operator overload during multi-robot missions.
Large investments and internal change of procedures and processes are required.
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>
Managing robots in the nuclear back-end presents inherent safety risks for the workforce, such as potential injuries during necessary interventions.
Long-term workforce sustainability is at risk because the nuclear industry struggles to recruit younger workers. The need for experts in robots, AI, and maintenance is also growing at the same time. This issue necessitates attracting younger people and upskilling the current workforce.
Automation introduces concerns over job displacement, potentially leading to opposition from labour groups and communities. These concerns emphasise the importance of managing transitions thoughtfully to minimise workforce disruption while advancing automation responsibly.
Limited funding impacts the research, development, and deployment of critical AI and robotics technologies, especially at early technology readiness levels (TRL 1-6). Securing targeted investments is essential to progressing high-value technologies through these foundational stages and making AI and robotics safer and more effective in the nuclear context.

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<p>The public may have concerns about the safety and environmental impact of using AI and robotics, especially in sensitive areas like nuclear decommissioning. Ethical considerations, including transparency, accountability, and the appropriate use of autonomous systems, could also be important to address to build public trust.</p>
<p>Policymakers could face pressures to protect local jobs and industries, which may complicate the regulatory aspects of automation. Such political pushback might underscore the importance of balanced deployment strategies that consider economic stability alongside technological integration.</p>

Table 6 Summary of Recommended Solutions for Subtask 5.2B

<i>General Aspects</i>
<p>Establish platforms to stimulate discussion between various stakeholders (e.g. to raise awareness of impediments and opportunities) and make the results and findings easy-to-access.</p>
<p>Creation of a test-bed facility for carrying out (cold) tests with automated and robotic systems under realistic conditions, which can be used by European developers/users.</p>
<i>Technical Aspects</i>
<p>Easy-to-access and maintained database on existing technologies, their use, approximate radiation tolerances, and practical parameters.</p>
<p>Standardisation and awareness of technology development, integration and deployment processes (including lifetime requirements such as maintenance).</p>
<p>Focus on modular designs that allow systems to be reconfigured for different purposes, minimising single-purpose use and ensuring that systems can evolve.</p>
<p>Implement simulation and code analysis approaches to verify and validate the safety and efficacy of automation and robotic systems in operating environments.</p>

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<i>Environmental Aspects</i>
Consideration in the design process that the system is easy to decontaminate and dispose of and ensure that the systems can be maintained and repaired by third parties (sustainability, waste reduction).
Engage the public and stakeholders through transparent communication about the potential risks, safety and environmental benefits of using automated and robotic systems in the nuclear back-end.
Development of international standards and guidelines that address the mandatory requirements for robots for nuclear back-end tasks.
Early dialogue between technology developers/providers and regulators to better understand functional and certification requirements.
Graded approach to address the level of automation, ranging from remotely controlled systems to autonomous systems.
<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Focus on tasks for which automated or robotics systems offer clear safety and/or economic benefits.
Methodology for Cost-Benefit-Analysis (CBA) with a reasonable assessment of risks. A CBA can provide justification for the business case and budget approval.
Need for international collaboration in the robotics community to use budgets efficiently.
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Provision of suitable training measures, for which digital tools can also be used.
Provision of standardised training courses developed by technology developers.
Allocation of sufficient budgets to build competencies, including upskilling.
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>
Involve operational personnel at all stages of design and development to ensure practical insights that enhance safety and usability.
Emphasise the benefits of robotics and automation for society and outline potential future applications to build support.

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Encourage activities and funding initiatives that support robotics and automated systems, including cross-industry exchanges to share insights and best practices.

Provide funding to advance promising technologies from TRL 1 to TRL 6, enabling the development and testing needed for future deployment.

Prioritise sustained investment in R&D focused on AI explainability, robotics autonomy, and safety mechanisms to ensure safe and effective use in sensitive environments.

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Appendix 3 – Summary of findings from subtask 5.2C

Table 7 Summary of Identified Barriers for Subtask 5.2C

<i>Technical Aspects</i>
Data Reliability and Management: There are concerns about whether existing sensor technologies provide sufficient data reliability.
Infrastructure Adequacy: There are mixed views on whether current infrastructures support secure data management necessary for DT/BIM implementation.
Need for Expertise: There is a consensus on the necessity of specialised expertise to navigate the complexities of these technologies within nuclear projects.
Cybersecurity Integration: While beneficial, integrating cybersecurity systems remains an area requiring further development.
Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) Solutions Limitation: The availability of ready-made solutions appears insufficient to meet specific industry needs.
AI Integration Challenges: Effective AI integration is still limited, suggesting room for growth in leveraging advanced analytics for decision support.
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>
Insufficient integration of environmental considerations in current DT and BIM solutions.
Inadequate regulatory frameworks to support the use of DT and BIM in the nuclear industry.
Uncertainty about the full potential of DT and BIM in improving sustainability throughout the decommissioning lifecycle.
Developers/end users are unaware of existing regulatory requirements (e.g. for safety and security aspects) that the technology has to fulfil, which can cause delays and project uncertainties.
Country-specific legislation and certification mechanisms

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<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Uncertainty about the economic justification for initial investments
Lack of concrete evidence demonstrating return on investment
Insufficient collaboration between nuclear industry stakeholders and technology providers
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Challenges in integrating DT and BIM with existing operational systems and processes
Uncertainty about the effectiveness of DT and BIM in improving operational resilience and cybersecurity incident response
Difficulties in aligning DT and BIM with established cybersecurity frameworks
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>
Lack of global standardisation and harmonisation of DT and BIM practices
Limited public acceptance and trust in digital technologies for nuclear decommissioning and waste management
Concerns about data privacy, cybersecurity, and potential misuse of DT and BIM data
Lack of high-quality leadership skills within senior management roles.

Table 8 Summary of Recommended Solutions for Subtask 5.2C

Summary of Recommended Solutions
<i>Technical Aspects</i>
Development of international standards and guidelines that address the mandatory requirements for DTs and BIM for nuclear back-end tasks

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<p>Invest in developing advanced sensor technologies specifically tailored for nuclear decommissioning environments to improve data accuracy and reliability.</p>
<p>Encourage the development of customised DT and BIM solutions that address the unique requirements of nuclear decommissioning projects, potentially through collaborations between technology providers and nuclear industry experts.</p>
<p>Implement robust data management systems with enhanced security features to ensure reliable and secure data handling throughout the decommissioning process.</p>
<p>Invest in research and development to improve AI and machine learning integration with DT and BIM, addressing data integration and system compatibility challenges.</p>
<p>Focus initial implementation efforts on high-priority applications such as dismantling scenario feasibility assessments and regulatory review support, gradually expanding to other use cases as the technology matures.</p>
<p>Develop standardised protocols and best practices for DT and BIM implementation in nuclear decommissioning to facilitate wider adoption and regulatory compliance.</p>
<p><i>Environmental Aspects</i></p>
<p>Develop more comprehensive DT and BIM solutions that explicitly incorporate environmental risk modelling and assessment capabilities.</p>
<p>Update and adapt regulatory frameworks to accommodate the integration of DT and BIM technologies in nuclear decommissioning projects.</p>
<p>Conduct further research and pilot projects to demonstrate the concrete benefits of DT and BIM in optimising resource utilisation and waste minimisation during decommissioning.</p>
<p>Establish industry-wide standards and best practices for integrating environmental considerations into DT and BIM solutions specific to nuclear decommissioning.</p>
<p>Provide training and education programs for regulators and industry professionals to enhance understanding of DT and BIM applications in environmental risk management and sustainability.</p>

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Encourage collaboration between technology developers, environmental experts, and regulatory bodies to ensure DT and BIM solutions meet both technical and regulatory requirements.
Implement monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the effectiveness of DT and BIM in improving environmental outcomes and sustainability in decommissioning projects.
Incremental approach to replacement of conventional methods with DT and BIM
<i>Commercial Aspects</i>
Conduct comprehensive cost-benefit analyses and develop case studies that clearly demonstrate the long-term economic benefits of DT and BIM implementation in nuclear decommissioning projects.
Establish pilot projects to showcase the potential cost savings and operational efficiencies gained through DT and BIM adoption, providing tangible evidence of return on investment.
Create industry-wide platforms or forums to facilitate collaboration between nuclear sector stakeholders and technology providers, to encourage the development of tailored DT and BIM solutions.
Develop standardised metrics and key performance indicators to measure and communicate the economic impact of DT and BIM adoption in nuclear decommissioning projects.
Implement phased adoption strategies that allow for gradual investment and integration of DT and BIM technologies, reducing upfront costs and risks.
Explore public-private partnerships or government incentives to offset initial investment costs and encourage wider adoption of DT and BIM in the nuclear sector.
<i>Operational Aspects</i>
Develop comprehensive integration strategies that address the complexities of incorporating DT and BIM into existing nuclear facility operations. This may involve creating detailed transition plans and conducting thorough impact assessments.
Implement pilot projects to demonstrate the practical benefits of DT and BIM in enhancing operational efficiency and safety. Use these projects to gather concrete data on performance improvements.

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<p>Invest in specialised training programs for nuclear facility staff to build expertise in utilising DT and BIM technologies within the unique context of nuclear operations.</p>
<p>Collaborate with cybersecurity experts to develop robust frameworks that integrate DT and BIM capabilities with existing security protocols. This should include conducting thorough risk assessments and developing mitigation strategies.</p>
<p>Create a centralised knowledge-sharing platform for the nuclear industry to exchange experiences, challenges, and solutions related to DT and BIM implementation.</p>
<p>Engage with regulatory bodies to develop guidelines that support the safe and effective integration of DT and BIM technologies within the nuclear sector's stringent operational requirements.</p>
<p><i>Socio-Political Aspects</i></p>
<p>Launch public education and engagement campaigns to improve understanding of DT and BIM technologies and their benefits in nuclear decommissioning and waste management. This could include transparent communication about safety measures and potential environmental benefits.</p>
<p>Leverage the appeal of advanced digital technologies to attract younger professionals to the nuclear sector by highlighting career opportunities in DT and BIM implementation.</p>
<p>Collaborate with academic institutions to develop specialised training programs that combine nuclear engineering expertise with digital skills, preparing the future workforce for the digitalised nuclear industry.</p>
<p>Promote collaboration between countries to share best practices, standardise approaches, and address common challenges in implementing DT and BIM technologies. Create cross-functional teams or working groups within organisations.</p>
<p>Create collaborations between government agencies, nuclear industry stakeholders, and technology providers to drive innovation and adoption of DT and BIM.</p>
<p>Demonstrate how the adoption of DT and BIM in nuclear back-end aligns with broader sustainability and environmental protection objectives to gain political and public support.</p>